

Techniques for Designing Broadband Asymmetrical Multi-section Wilkinson Power Divider

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Abstract:

Here we will provide a review on broadband asymmetrical multi-section Wilkinson power divider and try to identify the technical strengths as well as the weaknesses of the same. A numerical technique based on the method of least squares (MLS) was presented for the design as well as the optimization of a Wilkinson power divider for arbitrary power division between its output ports within a specified frequency bandwidth enabled by source and load impedance matching. In the paper, we will describe our optimum design of the Wilkinson power divider with the proposed MLS procedure by means of (a) full-wave simulations and (b) fabrication and measurement of two separate designs.

Introduction:

In principle, as stated in the paper itself, power dividers vary widely across designs' having specific advantages and disadvantages. Following its invention in 1960, the Wilkinson power divider is one of the important power divider design with completely matched output ports as well as sufficiently high isolation between them. Now, at least in theory, this power divider design is also potentially lossless if no reflected power from output ports enters into it. From such perspective, this divider has wide applications in microwave circuits and antenna feeds. However, the major bottleneck is its narrow bandwidth (as compared to a conventional resistive power divider), which has the best performance at a center design frequency. The authors in the paper itself give a brief review of several schemes which were devised in the past (at least until the year 2006 i.e. when the paper was written) to increase the bandwidth of operation of these power divider.

In the author's own language from the paper, they state "*The main proposal was made in 1968 [1-2], which used series connection of several sections having considerably increased bandwidth and high isolation between outputs for equal power division. A device for unequal power division between outputs was proposed in 1965 [3]. The even- and odd-mode analysis was employed for a single-section Wilkinson power divider. A procedure based on the even- and odd-mode analysis*

was used for the design of a three-port multi-section power divider with unequal output powers in 1971 [4]. It should be noted that the even- and odd-mode method of analysis is useful for axially symmetric circuits. It is not applicable to asymmetrical circuits”. Furthermore, they also write, “However, the method devised for determination of scattering matrix elements was applicable for the case of neglecting dispersion and dissipation effects. In recent years, several schemes have been proposed to decrease the size of transmission lines in order to facilitate their application in microwave integrated circuits (MICs) and monolithic microwave integrated circuits (MMICs) [5], [6]. A power divider was proposed and fabricated using lumped components and compensation capacitors for increasing frequency bandwidths [7].”

1. Strengths of the paper

The following could be summarized as the strengths of the paper:

1. In this paper, the authors tackled a relatively challenging problem of designing an *asymmetrical power divider circuit* operating across a large bandwidth. They achieved this with the help an optimization procedure based on the method of least squares (MLS) coupled with an even- and odd-mode analysis to determine the initial element sizes (namely, the widths and lengths of metallic strips and values of resistors).

2. They demonstrate multi-section Wilkinson powers divider for arbitrary power division together with source and load impedance matching in a specified frequency bandwidth.
3. This was the first time dispersion and dissipation models of microstrip were incorporated into the proposed procedure. The performance of the dividers by the three methods (i.e., MLS, software, and measurements) were compared, which indicated the efficacy of the proposed design and optimization method of least squares.
4. From an optimization point of view, the authors considered the Wilkinson power divider to be divided into two networks. First, the transmission and admittance matrices were determined, and then the scattering matrix of the device were calculated. This lead to the construction of an error function over the required frequency bandwidth to provide the required power division between output ports, by minimizing the reflected power from the input port, and maximizing the isolation among output ports. The error function were also made to depend on the metallic strip widths, lengths, and values of resistors. Minimization of the error function determined their optimum design values. In short, a multi-objective figure of merit function was used. This has an important advantage associated with it. The advantage comes from the perspective, that a specification for an arbitrary phase difference between its outputs in a frequency bandwidth and

minimization of the insertion loss may be incorporated into the expression of the error function to realize highly error-tolerant circuits.

5. The “Fmincon” function of MATLAB software was used for optimization of the error function [8-32]. Now, Fmincon uses a sequential quadratic programming (SQP) method. In this method, a QP sub problem is solved at each iteration. Fmincon uses the Broyden, Fletcher, Goldfarb, and Shanno (BFGS) quasi-Newton method with a mixed quadratic and cubic line search procedure. This class of algorithms is based on Newton’s method, but it is a bit different from the conventional technique in a way that it does not require calculation of second derivatives. In essence, these are called quasi-Newton methods. They update an approximate Hessian matrix at each iteration of the algorithm. The update is computed as a function of the gradient. In the scientific literature, it is already shown that conjugate gradient methods and quasi-Newton methods are one of the best-favored methods that use gradient information. The BFGS quasi-Newton method requires more computation in each iteration and more storage than the conjugate gradient methods, although it generally converges in fewer iterations. Therefore, it can be concluded that the optimization algorithm used were one of the fastest methods even by today’s standard even after 15 years of its first publication.

Finally, in the author's own words *“The proposed procedure based on the MLS designs and optimizes an asymmetrical multisection Wilkinson power divider and determines its configuration for any specification of arbitrary power division ratio between its outputs and complex impedance matching among its input and output ports (namely, source and load impedances) in a specified frequency bandwidth. Therefore, the significance of the design method is the provision of arbitrary power division, impedance matching, and the realization of the broadest possible bandwidth. Furthermore, the available design methods for the Wilkinson power divider are not developed to minimize insertion loss, realization of arbitrary phase difference between output ports, and complex impedance matching among input and output ports in a specified frequency bandwidth. Such specifications may be readily incorporated into the design procedure by the MLS.”*

2. Weaknesses of the paper

The following could be summarized as the weakness of the paper:

1. Coming from an algorithm background, I can comprehend that the optimization algorithm used were one of the fastest. However, I strongly believe that the authors needed to quantify with some visual aids i.e. 1-2 plots to highlight how fast their method converges to the solution with respect to any of the approaches previously used. The authors in contrast, focused their discussion much more, on

“How did they define a good Figure of Merit (error function) for their device and select their initial parameters?” From this perspective, I am on the opinion that the authors did not generalize their approach such that it can be of interest to people working in other fields of science (This is also the reason why the paper was published in a specialized journal and not an “inter-disciplinary” one).

2. Another important observation was that the authors show with FDTD simulations that bandwidth of up to 20 GHz can be achieved for the devices using their technique. However, in the later section, when they went about fabricating and measuring some of their designed samples, the designed and measured bandwidth was only ~3 GHz. This is one of the major drawbacks of the paper. Moreover, they never explicitly quantify in any of their text as to why they had chosen to go into experiments with devices which have < 10x bandwidth than their designs in simulations.
3. In addition to this, another point, which comes up here, is “What is the broadest bandwidth that they could have designed with their approach? Is 20 GHz the best? If yes, then what are the limiting factors for their approach? In no, then how much could they have extended it?” The authors could have had a paragraph on this.
4. Speaking of N-port power dividers, the authors could also have quantified how well does the algorithm scale with the growing number of ports in the system.

Was not clear from the discussion they had for the 3-port and 4-port power dividers that they designed.

5. Finally, the authors attributed that the deviation of the experimental results from the simulations was due to the use of circuit elements whose values were close to the optimized values that was achieved with the algorithm. They also reported that they later went ahead and incorporated this constraint in the optimization routine again and re-optimized it. Still we see some deviation. It would have been better if the authors could also have quantified the areas from which errors might have propagated in the design. However, the error in simulations and measurements was still within acceptable range for publication but not enough for an industrial adaptation at that stage.

Conclusion

Since this was one of the earliest demonstration of an *asymmetrical power divider circuit* operating across a large bandwidth, I believe that the paper was interesting to read and learn more about the exciting approaches in trying to design them. The theory was very well laid out in terms of how the authors went from defining the scattering matrix of the entire system (as well as the admittance matrix, transmission matrix and the ABCD matrix) to incorporating the same in their error function. The lectures on defining and characterizing these matrices in the Microwave Engineering-I class really helped me to grasp the concepts in the paper fast without having to waste much time. I could follow very nicely how they transitioned from theory into defining a very logical error function for their device, which was guided, by the theory of microwave circuits.

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